

POSSIBILITIES OF QUANTUM CRYPTOGRAPHY IN PROVIDING CYBER SECURITY IN NETWORKS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10940204>

Abstract: Today, the rapid development of digital technologies on a global scale provides a wide range of opportunities and conveniences in people's lives. It also creates cyber security issues. It is important to ensure the security of data of cyberspace users. Therefore, quantum cryptography is one of the modern technologies for ensuring data security in the use of digital technologies in cyberspace. In this article, a number of possibilities of modern technology to ensure the security of online communication channels using the concepts of quantum mechanics are presented.

Keywords: Resources, threats, privacy, integrity, information, vulnerabilities, communication tools, potential, privacy.

Currently, all developing countries are paying a lot of attention to information technologies. This creates the basis for the development of digital technologies. Also, we all know that cyber threats are increasing in the process of information exchange in networks. If we look at it from this point of view, modern cyber security technologies are definitely needed to protect against modern cyber threats, and the development and improvement of these technologies is one of the important tasks. One such modern technology is quantum cryptography technology. This technology is a type of encryption that provides online communication channels using quantum mechanics concepts. In other words, it encodes and decodes signals using the principles of quantum physics, making it incredibly difficult for anyone to intercept them or carry out similar threats.

A quantum-secure network highlights the ever-increasing importance of adopting a quantum-secure infrastructure that is immune to attack due to the growing threat of quantum computing to current cryptographic standards. The focus will be on the urgency of businesses and organizations upgrading their cybersecurity infrastructure to protect against potential quantum computing breaches. In cybersecurity, "quantum security" is crucial because of the potential of quantum computing to break encryption. This emerging cyberspace focuses

on developing quantum-resistant algorithms to protect digital communications from quantum threats. With quantum computers poised to break traditional cryptography, the urgency for quantum security innovations is paramount. This proactive approach, supported by institutions such as NIST, seeks to ensure a cybersecurity infrastructure that can withstand the advanced computing power of quantum technology, thus protecting our digital future from potential breaches.

Quantum computing is fundamentally different from the laptops and smartphones we depend on today. Instead of ever-smaller transistors, quantum machines operate on the principles of particle physics and excel at solving complex statistical problems with multiple variables. Although quantum computing is not a complete reality today, it has the potential to add significant value to fields such as medical research, artificial intelligence, weather forecasting, military affairs, and cyber security. Ironically, it creates a significant cybersecurity threat that requires a change in how we encrypt our data.

Because quantum computers can process data at exponential speeds, they pose significant cyber threats to existing cryptosystems. However, current quantum computers do not have the hardware needed to break this algorithm. Many applications, including web browsers, online payments, digital signatures, and email, rely on asymmetric encryption schemes such as the rsa algorithm. The RSA algorithm is based on the fact that conventional computers cannot find the factors of the product of two large prime numbers. A quantum computer with 4,000 qubits and 100 million gates is required to crack a 2,048-bit RSA key. Other public-key encryption schemes such as Diffie-Hellman and ECC will be ineffective in the face of a quantum computer. On the one hand, this disrupts the encryption ecosystem; on the other hand, it exposes potentially sensitive information from previously exfiltrated encrypted data from various historical cyberattacks by nation-state groups and cybercriminals.

Standardized post-quantum cryptographic algorithms aim to create secure systems against both quantum and conventional computers that are compatible with existing communication protocols and networks. Companies like Utimaco are investing in post-quantum cryptography to offer quantum-resistant solutions, protecting systems from potential quantum computer-based attacks. A hash function is a process that converts plaintext data of any size into a unique, fixed-length ciphertext known as a "digest". This function takes a string and outputs a digest of some length, usually 256 to 512 bits.

Common cryptographic hash functions include SHA2, SHA3, and Blake2. hash-based signature schemes are based on one-time signature schemes (OTS), where a key pair is used only once to sign a message. Using an OTS key pair for multiple messages compromises security because it allows for signature forgery. Recent hash-based signature schemes such as Xms, Leighton-Micali (LMS), Sphinx, and BPQS offer improved performance. Most are stateful, requiring secret keys that are updated with each use. However, Sphinx is stateless and has larger signatures than stateful schemes like xms and LMS. Designed for blockchain systems, BPQS and Sphinx use vots+ and HORST multiple signature mechanisms. NIST has chosen to standardize three digital signature algorithms for quantum-secure signatures: Crystals-Dilithium, FALCON, and Sphinx+. This decision is based on an understanding of quantum security and hash-based signatures.

There are two ways to protect data using quantum cryptography, including using longer keys (2048 bits or longer) and protecting messages with symmetric encryption and using asymmetric encryption for keys (such as the TLS standard). Also, some advantages of quantum cryptography include: Figure 1

Figure 1. Some advantages of quantum cryptography.

Despite its powerful potential, quantum cryptography is rarely used today due to limitations associated with the technology.

A single quantum switch requires a single photon laser beam signal through a fiber optic cable. Only one photon passes through at a time, making the process slower than current communication methods. Quantum key

distribution requires a special fiber-optic cable between the sender and the receiver, which complicates things further.

Automating the management of quantum-secure certificates allows enterprises to adapt their cryptographic approach to rapidly evolving quantum-secure cryptography methodologies.

Enterprises can use automation tools like Sectigo Certificate Manager and Digicert to renew certificates with quantum secure certificates. These tools also facilitate new certificates and certificate renewals.

Post-quantum cryptography is a term that refers to traditional cryptographic algorithms that rely on public keys. These algorithms may be vulnerable to quantum attacks.

Physical distances also limit the use of quantum cryptography, as fiber optic cables require repeaters to transmit data across oceans. These repeaters cannot be used to distribute quantum keys.

Differences between traditional cryptography and quantum cryptography

Comparison point	Traditional cryptography	Quantum cryptography
Justified	Mathematical calculation	Quantum mechanics
Digital signature	Yes	No
Placement	Placed	Still in its early stages
Communication tool	Independent	I depend
Bit rate	Relies on computing power	1 MBPS (average)

On the other hand, quantum cryptography is an encryption technology that uses quantum mechanics to encrypt messages, making them unbreakable.

Types of quantum secure certificates. There are 3 types of quantum secure certificates, which can be summarized in the table below:

Certificate	Description
Quantum Safe	Quantum Secure Certificates
Hybrid	Has both traditional and quantum secure keys
Composite	Multiple conventional and quantum secure keys

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adopting a quantum-secure infrastructure that is immune to attack due to the growing threat of quantum computing to current cryptographic standards. This development raises concerns about the potential to break modern cryptography, making current data encryption methods obsolete, such as the trio of examples mentioned earlier. The need for new cryptography to combat these powerful machines is looming. Traditional encryption methods such as RSA and elliptic curve can be easily solved by quantum computers, greatly reducing the time it takes to crack security keys from years to hours. Quantum computers capable of breaking current codes may be more than a decade away, experts say, but cybersecurity calls for immediate action.

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